

The essence structure and main functions of worldview

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Abstract: This article highlights the features of the manifestation of national values in the life of our society, the types of values, the role of values in human life.

Key words: Moral, Religious, Legal, Political, Ecological, Aesthetic

The main part. The concept of world view. Each person will have his own vision of the world, his own vision of himself and others, life and the universe, his conclusions. These visions, concepts, views and conclusions determine the meaning of the attitude of a particular person to other people and their daily activities. In this sense, a worldview is a system of views, visions, knowledge about reality, the essence, structure of the universe, its place in it, surrounding the tevarak environment of a person. Worldview is the perception, perception and knowledge of the universe in the most general way. A form of worldview inherent in one person or individual is called an individual worldview. A set of worldviews specific to a group, party, nation, or society as a whole is referred to as a social worldview. It can be said that a social worldview is born from the sum of individual worldviews. In this case, it is necessary to take into account both general and private forms of social worldview. On the basis of everyday life experiences, views, concepts, ideas are formed in society, people with a simple, self-developing (stichian) essence. It is a self-developing (stichian) form of worldview. It is also often called life philosophy. The scope of life philosophy is very wide and includes both simple forms of manifestation of consciousness and rational and healthy thoughts. A person of a specific type of life philosophy or a simple practical worldview. The content of this concept is manifested in a person's attitude to the world, events and phenomena, to others and their activities, to such many concepts as his own life and its content, his understanding, understanding, appreciation of them. The philosophical worldview is formed and developed under the influence of everyday activities, secular, religious, scientific knowledge, life observations and social upbringing. In science, all aspects of social existence are KS. It is natural

that emotion, reason and thinking also play an important role in the formation of a worldview. Its formation also depends on the emotional experiences and moods of people, and a person's mood reflects his life circumstances, social condition, national character, cultural level, personal fate, age, etc. In the worldview of a particular period, the spirit of the time, the mood, aspiration of social forces also find expression. For example, the need to strengthen the independence of today's Uzbekistan has a tremendous impact on the formation of the worldview of independence. The philosophical worldview has a complex structure. It consists of components such as certain knowledge, ideas and goals aimed at the future, achievements of natural and social science, religious visions, values, trust, belief, thought, emotion. Within this, faith is important. It is one of the foundations that make up the content of the worldview. Belief arises from a person's deep belief in the correctness of their views and ideas, the validity of their dreams, the suitability of their activities and behavior for common goals and requirements. It determines the EMotion, will and activity of a person, controls them, encourages the individual to factor, to productive activities. The essence of the worldview. About the formation of a much more developed worldview of a person from this period, and about the worldview of people as a whole, a set of accumulated knowledge, practical skills, emerging values, perceptions of himself and the world that surrounds himselfn this, a person distinguishes between what is acceptable and what is unacceptable, gives assessments, creates a system of priorities and acts in an appropriate way in achieving certain goals. Hence, in the worldview, the functions of cognition, attitude to values and determination of behavior are embodied. The cognitive function of the worldview includes all questions of interest in a person, as well as finding answers in a certain way. Knowing enriches and expands the worldview of people, it becomes more thoughtful and richer in content, depending on the development of society. But the world is very colorful and goes through a continuous process of change, while questions that do not have satisfactory answers are more than questions that can be answered unequivocally. Therefore, the worldview, questions and answers of every person who approaches

problems in a certain way are always characterized by personal originality and, at least for the same reason, never resemble the worldview of other people. The inextricable connection of the intellectual, emotional and spiritual foundations of the worldview and their validity as absolutely certain, individual characteristics for each person without jamuljam. Intellectual, emotional and spiritual foundations in harmony with Will, beliefs – bring to the surface views that people actively accept, which correspond to their level of consciousness and goals in life. An important element of the worldview is skepticism, which avoids the perception of the worldview as dogmatism, that is, homogeneity, unrealistic thinking, one rule or another, an indisputable fact. The opposite of dogmatism is skepticism, in which doubt becomes absolute, becomes the main factor in thinking, applies as a general principle of cognition and perception of being. The structure of the worldview consists of the most important elements, such as perception of the world, perception of the world and understanding of the world. Since the philosophical worldview, in essence, is a spiritual activity, it gave rise to certain directions of a conscious, human attitude towards being. For example, the moral relations of people in society – in moral worldviews, legal relations – legal, political relations – political, religious relations – religious, environmental relations – are expressed in forms of ecological worldview. Interpreting this in the system style, it will look like this:

1. Moral.
2. Religious.
3. Legal.
4. Political.
5. Ecological.
6. Aesthetic.

The relatively independent forms of worldview that made up this system act in interdependence, in connection. The level of development of the worldview system corresponds to and represents the development of society. In addition, in each historical period, the development of the nation is manifested in its mentality and worldview. In other words, the worldview system and their characteristics

determine the spiritual image of a particular person, social group, class and whole nation. The concept of "worldview" is formed in close connection with such feelings and concepts as self-awareness, patriotism, national pride, historical memory, spiritual perfection. Because it is through these mental-social phenomena that the worldview becomes clear, becomes a historical piece of universal values. Historical forms of the philosophical worldview were the legitimate result of human development and manifested as a spiritual criterion for the development of society. In the early stages of development, the attitude of people to nature, to their social life was expressed in various narratives and legends. They thus formed a mythological worldview. The reverence of good in the struggle between evil and goodness is evidenced by the humanistic content of the mythological worldview. In particular, the narrative, myth, and which were created in the process of civilization of the Uzbek people". The fact that religion, including Islam, has existed steadily for thousands of years, suggests that it is deeply rooted in human nature, fulfilling several tasks that are unique to it. First of all, religion, a certain sphere of spiritual life of society, group, individual person, has absorbed the norms of universal morality, revitalizing them, transforming them into mandatory rules of behavior for everyone"³. The absolutization of any, including the place and importance of a religious worldview in the life of society in its artificial disclosure, can cause negative consequences. This is especially evident in the current era, when religious fundamentalism and extremism have become a serious threat to humanity. With the intensification of Science, Technology, worldly Science in the current era, it is also necessary to emphasize that "a religious worldview is not the only way of thinking, of treating the world that surrounds a person, of people like himself. Secular thought, a secular lifestyle, has also developed side by side with him and with the right to live on an equal footing with him"⁴. Religious worldview is studied by a philosophical science called theology. Theology has created a unique perfect system as well as analyzing issues such as the world and human attitude, the meaning of life, the problem of life and death in connection with theological, religious concepts of faith. Today, among the main tasks of a talay of a religious worldview, its regulatory activities related to the elimination of life conflicts are extremely important. In general, the role and importance of religion in the upbringing of a harmonious generation is incredibly huge, and it is growing. The main directions of the philosophical worldview. The worldview system and each of the relatively independent directions inherent in it can be viewed as an enlightened (concretized) form of philosophical reasoning. A philosophical worldview, to put it simply, is a system of knowledge that expresses a person's attitude to the universe, man and being.

If logical consistency is violated, it undermines the impartial, scientific, clear and consistent reflection of the worldview of the outside world. 4. The universality of a philosophical worldview is characterized by the fact that it constitutes the content

of other forms of worldview, that is, any form of worldview has its own philosophical character. 5. The philosophical worldview is purposeful and corresponds to human interests. Because a person lives with a certain goal, dreams, reflects them in his worldview.

6. The ideological principle of the philosophical worldview is expressed in the fact that a certain idea lies on its basis. In particular, today's Uzbek national philosophical worldview is characterized by its reliance on the idea of national independence, self-realization, independence that determines the future of our nation. The philosophical worldview serves to transform this idea into a belief and its fulfillment.

7. One of the most important principles of a philosophical worldview is the unity of theory and practice. The existence of a worldview as a theory is explained by the fact that social practice is able to creatively summarize its experiences and determine perspective plans. Also, in the process of practical introduction of the worldview, its methods and tools are important. Tasks (functions) of the philosophical worldview. The mentioned principles of the philosophical worldview determine its functions. That is, these tasks arise from the goals and interests of society in the universal spirit and have methodological significance for other forms of worldview. The worldview is primarily an expression of human relations. From this point of view, it is visible in the way in which a person reacts to being, initially in the way of his assessment. It refers to the evaluation task of a philosophical worldview. That is, a person, based on his own needs and interests, divides things-phenomena: good-bad, useful-harmful, rewards-sin, Oriya-benomuslik into opposite criteria. As a person evaluates things-phenomena,

For example, looking back at history, we see that at certain times the philosophical worldview was associated with the interests of the human being, uniting people around the idea of liberation that defines the future of the nation. This was evident during the period of the struggle against the Mongol invaders. This idea (philosophy of freedom), as a component of the worldview, United and mobilized different classes of the nation into a common struggle, regardless of faith, economic situation and political position. Any worldview comes from human needs, corresponding to its interests. At the same time, on the one hand, the worldview does not form on its own, that is, stichially. On the contrary, it arises as a result of the purposeful activities of various educational tools. On the second hand, a philosophical worldview, formed in contrast to the influence of universal consciousness (civilization), is a common form of various possibilities and means of educating a particular person, social group or nation. Consequently, the educational task of the philosophical worldview should be considered as the basis of other tasks mentioned above. It consists in the formation of a spirit of tolerance,

compromise, cultural resolution of any conflicts, hope and confidence in the future, based on the creation of a broad and thoughtful ability to think in people.

Summary.The scale of the worldview expresses the expanding aspect of the individual, which develops throughout his life. The content of the worldview reflects to what extent the diverse aspects of reality are covered in the mind of individ. The worldview center or focal point is understood as what kind of individual thinks about the universe from the framework of a complex of personal and social interests. A person relies on the living experience, the knowledge gained by people who have passed on himself before him in his life. The worldview acquires a great practical meaning by influencing the moral standards of people, their aspirations in life, their interests, their work and their lives[1]

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